

A STUDY OF VISCOSITY OF AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS OF POTASSIUM DICHROMATE

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Viscosity of aqueous solutions of potassium dichromate over a wide range of concentrations up to saturation has been determined at temperatures ranging from 30° to 60°. The variation of viscosity with temperature at any given concentration has been found to obey Andrade's exponential equation. The variation of viscosity with concentration at any given temperature has been found to obey another exponential equation, first observed by Suryanarayana and Venkatesan.

The purpose of the present investigation is two-fold, firstly to verify the equation of Suryanarayana and Venkatesan (*Acta Chim., Hung.*, 1958, 16, 149, 339, 345; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1958, 54, 1709; *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1958, 31, 442; *Monatsh.*, 1958, 89, 824) and secondly to examine the applicability of the equation of Andrade (*Nature*, 1930, 125, 309) as observed to be applicable to solutions of electrolytes by several others (Berl *et al.*, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1931, 152, 284; Joshi and Solanki, this *Journal*, 1940, 17, 630; Ram Gopal, *ibid.*, 1953, 30, 708; Suryanarayana and Venkatesan, *Acta Chim., Hung.*, 1958, 16, 451).

EXPERIMENTAL

Viscosity and density were determined as described in our earlier publications (*loc. cit.*).

Solubility data were obtained from Seidell ("Solubilities of Organic and Inorganic Compounds", Vol. I, Van Nostrand Co., New York, 1940) and A. Comey and D. Hahn ("A Dictionary of Chemical Solubilities, Inorganic", The Macmillan Co., London, 1921). Results obtained are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Molality.	Mole frac.	Viscosity (in centipoises) at							Const. of eq. (2)		E_{vis} (calc.)
		30°.	35°.	40°.	45°.	50°.	55°.	60°.	A.	B.	
0.280	0.005019	0.8335	0.7519	0.6841	0.6238	0.5762	0.5318	0.4903	0.002338	1778	3534
0.335	0.005998	0.8383	0.7563	0.6874	0.6269	0.5813	0.5348	0.4935	0.002375	1775	3529
0.390	0.006977	0.8424	0.7600	0.6907	0.6305	0.5857	0.5378	0.4968	0.002438	1769	3517
0.445	0.007952	0.8487	0.7679	0.6993	0.6378	0.5919	0.5441	0.5020	0.002531	1761	3499
0.500	0.008928	0.8553	0.7745	0.7060	0.6439	0.5987	0.5495	0.5071	0.002621	1753	3483
0.555	0.009900	0.8592	0.7789	0.7098	0.6492	0.6023	0.5542	0.5118	0.002765	1738	3463
1.24	0.019100	0.8648	0.7823	0.7125	0.6533	0.6059	0.5571	0.5169	0.002900	1725	3428
Saturation		0.8664	0.7975	0.7485	0.6984	0.6615	0.6198	0.5841	0.001115	1317	2619
Molality at saturation	..	0.6798	0.7938	0.9179	1.0870	1.2580	1.4280	1.5980			
Mole fraction at saturation		0.0121	0.0141	0.0163	0.0192	0.0222	0.025	0.02798			
η_{sp}	{(extrapol.)	..	0.8072	0.7261	0.6561	0.5984	0.5495	0.5093	0.4690		
	{(from Lange)	..	0.8007	0.7225	0.6560	0.5988	0.5494	0.5064	0.4688		
B	{(calc.)	..	0.0760	0.0951	0.1129	0.1506	0.1892	0.1986	0.2515		
	{(obs.)	..	0.0787	0.0988	0.1320	0.1538	0.1857	0.2022	0.2207		

DISCUSSION

A plot (not shown) of $\log \eta$ vs. C_p (the ratio of the mole fraction of the solute at the molar concentration under consideration to that at saturation) provides a straight line at each temperature. It is clear that aqueous solutions of potassium dichromate obey the equation of Suryanarayana and Venkatesan (*loc. cit.*):

$$\eta = \eta_0 \exp. [B' C_p] \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

The η_0 values computed from the intercepts on the graph compare favourably with the values of viscosity of water at the respective temperatures. Similarly, the values of the constant B' , computed from the slope at different temperatures excepting at 40° and 60° , compare well with the $\ln (\eta_{sat}/\eta_0)$ at saturation obtained experimentally.

Plots of $\log \eta$ vs. $1/T$ (not shown) are linear for all the eight concentrations, thus proving the applicability of Andrade's equation,

$$\eta = A. \exp. [-B'/T] \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

The last three columns of the table show the values of the constants A and B of equation (2). Eyring *et al.* (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1937, 41, 249; *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1937, 5, 726) derived Andrade's equation in the form:

$$\eta = A. \exp. [-E_{vis}/RT] \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

where E_{vis} is the energy of activation for viscous flow. The last column of the table shows almost the same value for E_{vis} at all concentrations excepting for the saturated concentrations for which it is smaller.

Equations (2) and (3) were originally meant to apply to pure liquids. We have shown from works in this laboratory that several electrolyte solutions obey equations (2) and (3). This points to a fundamentally same basis of viscosity both in pure liquids and solutions. We have indicated in different contexts that internal pressure of a liquid medium may perhaps be such a basis on which a generalised theory of viscosity of liquids may be built.